

ACCESS TO TECHNICAL TRAINING AND EMPLOYABILITY OF YOUNG ADULTS IN THE CITY OF LIKASI

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Abstract: This article is based on the mismatch between access to technical training and access to employment for young adults in the city of Likasi. Africa in general and the Democratic Republic of Congo in particular is mainly populated by a predominantly young population. As a result, these young people need employment and adequate training to have access to work in order to make themselves useful to themselves, their society, their homeland and all humanity. This article shows the difficulty that young people experience in having access to training and employment.

Keywords: access, training, employability, young adult.

1. INTRODUCTION

Youth employment in Africa as in the Democratic Republic of Congo continues to be at the heart of the concerns of all country leaders. It is fitting that the fifth African Union - European Union summit held in Abidjan decided to focus on the theme "Investing in youth for a sustainable future". The growing number of young African migrants in European and American countries in search of better living, raises questions about the difficulty that African youth encounter in making their way in the professional field.

After observation and discussion with young adults, parents and educational authorities who organize technical courses in the city of Likasi, we realized that after training young adults, their professional integration has become a headache, mainly in mining companies.

It is to the point that they are forced to go through other specific and additional training that requires substantial sums of money to spend beyond the normal school curriculum. The research setting is the city of Likasi which is a city located in the Democratic Republic of Congo, more precisely in the province of Haut Katanga one hundred and twenty kilometers from the capital. This city is full of several secondary and university educational establishments that receive several learners in the technical field in particular in different namely : : electricity; electronics, construction, automotive mechanics, general mechanics, metallurgy, cutting and sewing at the humanitarian level and many others at the higher and university level including: electrical engineering, electro-energetics, computer science, industrial construction, applied mechanics, automotive mechanics, mining, metallurgy, pure chemistry, geology, industrial electricity, ...

The population is made up of all secondary school students and higher education students who have followed an apprenticeship course in the technical field of the city of Likasi, from which we took as a sample. The young adults questioned were chosen based on the following criterion:

- Be a young adult whose age varies between 18 and 35 years old;
- Be a young adult who has studied in a technical education institution;

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

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- Have the required age to apply for a job as provided for by the labor code of our country;
- Have studied in a technical education institution in Likasi;
- Have followed a normal course;
- Not be a worker in a formal or informal structure;
- Not have problems with the law.

Table 1: Description of the population

Category	Number	percentage
Humanity technician	20	50
University technician	20	50
Total	40	100

The results of this table show us that out of 40 respondents who constitute our study population; 20 young adult technicians or 50 percent come from basic training in a technical education institution at the humanitarian level and 20 others, or 50 percent, come from higher and university level technical training in our environment.

In order to collect the information to be analyzed, it is necessary to use an investigation tool. Indeed, the production of data is carried out using instruments such as: questionnaire, test, interview. As for us, we opted for the questionnaire.

For this purpose, to collect information relating to our work, we submitted the questionnaire to forty young adults who had followed a normal course in a technical education establishment in Likasi, chosen as a sample. All the respondents responded and we then all retrieved the grid of questions administered to each of them.

2. PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

The presentation of the various data is done in a double-entry table as recommended by the standards in force in educational sciences. Each table will be accompanied by a commentary that will shed light on the numerical data it contains.

3. RESULTS OF THE INDEPENDENT VARIABLE

The independent variable relates to access to employment for young adults after a training course in a given technical field. In this part, we present the data and results relating to the latter. In the following lines, we present the research questions relating to the independent variable. These questions are as follows:

Theme 1: basic training and access to employment

Table 2 below shows the results relating to basic training and access to employability for young adults in the city of Likasi.

- Null hypothesis: the training received on the study bench does not allow direct access to employment.
- Alternative hypothesis: the training received on the study bench may or may not allow you to directly access a job.

Table 2: presentation and analysis of data relating to basic training and access to employability

Answer (k)	f ₀	f _t	f ₀ -f _t	(f ₀ -f _t) ²	(f ₀ -f _t) ² /f _t
Yes	17	20	-3	9	0.45
No	23	20	3	9	0.45
Total	40		0	18	0.9

The theoretical frequency f_t being respectively 17 and 23 for the observed frequencies

f₀ of 20; the degree of freedom is then: Df=k-1=2-1=1, From where: the calculated value is worth: 0.9; the tabular value at the threshold of 0.05 (5%) being 3.84

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 11, Issue 6, pp: (59-68), Month: November - December 2024, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

The data in Table 3 above show that out of 40 participants, 17 say yes against 23 who say the opposite. The degree of freedom being equal to 1, gives at the threshold of 0.05 a tabulated Chi-square value of 3.84 higher than the calculated Chi-square of 0.9.

Conclusion: In view of the results obtained by calculation through the data in Table 3, we affirm that access to employment is difficult in our environment after an apprenticeship course in an educational establishment. To do this, let us confirm the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis.

THEME 2: Access to employment for young adult technicians in Likasi

Table 3 below shows the results relating to access to employment for young adult technicians in our environment after a course.

Null hypothesis: access to employment in Likasi is easy.

Alternative hypothesis: access to employment in Likasi is difficult.

Table 3: presentation and analysis of data relating to access to employment for young adult technicians.

Answer (k)	f_0	f_t	$f_0 - f_t$	$(f_0 - f_t)^2$	$(f_0 - f_t)^2 / f_t$
Extremely difficult	10	8	2	4	0.5
Very difficult	8	8	0	0	0
Difficult	16	8	8	64	8
Easy	6	8	-2	4	0.5
Very easy	0	8	-8	64	8
Total	40	136			17

The theoretical frequency f_t being respectively 10, 8, 16, 6 and 0 for the observed frequencies f_0 of 8; the degree of freedom is then: $Df = k - 1 = 5 - 1 = 4$; From where: the calculated value is worth: 17; the tabulated value at the threshold of 0.05 (5%) being 9.49

The data in Table 4 above show that out of 40 participants, 10 say that access to employment is extremely difficult; 8 say that it is very difficult; 16 say that it is difficult; and 6 think the opposite. The degree of freedom being equal to 4, gives at the threshold of 0.05 a tabulated Chi-square value of 9.49 lower than the calculated Chi-square of 17.

Conclusion: In view of the results obtained by calculation through the data in Table III.4; access to employment after an apprenticeship course is difficult in our environment. To do this, we reject the null hypothesis.

THEME 3: Entrepreneurship in relation to the technical field followed

Table 4 below shows the results relating to the possibility of undertaking an activity relating to the technical training field followed in our environment.

Null hypothesis: not all technical fields offer the possibility for young adult technicians to undertake in the event of a lack of employment.

Alternative hypothesis: all technical fields offer the possibility for young adult technicians to undertake in the event of a lack of employment

Table 4: presentation and analysis of data relating to entrepreneurship

Answer (k)	f_0	f_t	$f_0 - f_t$	$(f_0 - f_t)^2$	$(f_0 - f_t)^2 / f_t$
Yes for some sectors	27	20	7	49	2.45
No for others	13	20	-7	49	2.45
Total	40		0	18	4.9

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 11, Issue 6, pp: (59-68), Month: November - December 2024, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

The theoretical frequency f_t being respectively 27 and 13 for the observed frequencies

f_0 of 20; the degree of freedom is then: $Df=k-1=2-1=1$; From where: the calculated value is worth: 4.9 the tabulated value at the threshold of 0.05 (5%) being 3.84

The data in table 5 above show that out of 40 participants, 27 say yes for certain sectors against 13 who say the opposite. The degree of freedom being equal to 1, gives at the threshold of 0.05 a tabulated Chi-square value of 3.84 lower than the calculated Chi-square of 4.9.

Conclusion: In view of the results obtained by calculation through the data in table 5, we affirm that the possibility of undertaking in several areas of technical training is there; and this implies confidence on the part of consumers of the services offered. To do this, we reject the null hypothesis.

4. RESULT OF THE DEPENDENT VARIABLE

The dependent variable is related to basic technical training. In this section, we present the data and results relating to the latter through the following themes:

THEME 4: Reason for extracurricular or para-academic training before employment

Table 5 below shows the results relating to the different reasons for the merits of extracurricular training before employment.

Null hypothesis: the subject studied during the course is not sufficient to directly enter a profession and requires other training before employment.

Alternative hypothesis: the subject studied during the course is sufficient for employment.

Table 5: Presentation and analysis of data relating to the merits of extracurricular training before employment

Answer (k)	f_0	f_t	$f_0 - f_t$	$(f_0 - f_t)^2$	$(f_0 - f_t)^2 / f_t$
Incompatibility	14	10	4	16	1.6
Insufficient content	9	10	-1	1	0.1
Lack of suitable preparation	10	10	0	0	0
Desire to complete one's studies	7	10	-3	9	0.9
Total	40	26			2.6

The theoretical frequency f_t being respectively 14, 9, 10 and 7 for the observed frequencies

f_0 of 10; the degree of freedom is then: $Df=k-1=4-1=3$; From where: the calculated value is: 2.6; the tabulated value at the threshold of 0.05 (5%) being 7.82

The data in Table 6 above show that out of 40 participants, 14 speak of the incompatibility between the training received in an establishment and the technological realities of the position applied for; 9 speak of the inadequacy of the content received in different specific courses; 10 speak of a lack of preparation adapted to professional integration; and 7 speak of the desire on the part of the young adult to perfect his or her studies as the reason for seeking other extracurricular training. The degree of freedom being equal to 3, gives at the threshold of 0.05 a tabulated Chi-square value of 7.82 higher than the calculated Chi-square of 2.6.

Conclusion: In view of the results obtained by calculation through the data in Table III.2; the reason that would push young adults to request specific training before applying for a job would be the incompatibility between the training received at school and the technological realities of the position applied for. To do this, we confirm the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis.

THEME 5: Need for extracurricular training before integrating into a company and content of the subjects to be integrated into the training

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 11, Issue 6, pp: (59-68), Month: November - December 2024, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Table 6 below summarizes the results relating to the need for post-school or academic training and the subjects to be learned during this training.

Null hypothesis: extracurricular training remains necessary and must be provided in such a way as to fill the gaps before integrating into professional life.

Alternative hypothesis: Extracurricular training is not necessary and should not be given too long after a training course in a technical institution.

Table 6: Presentation and analysis of data relating to the need for extracurricular training before employment and subject.

Answer (k)	f_0	f_t	$f_0 - f_t$	$(f_0 - f_t)^2$	$(f_0 - f_t)^2 / f_t$
Sufficient at school	5	10	-5	25	2.5
Practices access to new technologies felt	21	10	11	121	12.1
Entrepreneurship	5	10	-5	25	2.5
Missing concepts	9	10	-1	1	0.1
Total	40			172	18.2

The theoretical frequency f_t being respectively 5, 21, 5 and 9 for the observed frequencies

f_0 of 10; the degree of freedom is then: $Df = k - 1 = 4 - 1 = 3$; From where: the calculated value is: 2.6; the tabulated value at the threshold of 0.05 (5%) being 7.82

The data in Table 7 above show that out of 40 participants, 5 say that it is not necessary to do another training after an apprenticeship course; 21 say that it is necessary to do this training on practical concepts relating to felt technology; 5 say that this training should be oriented towards entrepreneurship; and 9 say that this training is necessary on the subjects missing for young adults. The degree of freedom being equal to 3, gives at the threshold of 0.05 a tabulated Chi-square value of 7.82 lower than the calculated Chi-square of 18.2.

Conclusion: In view of the results obtained by calculation through the data in Table III.3; the need for extracurricular training is a real need in our environment in certain subjects relating to the practice not learned by the young adult during his course, with a particular emphasis on felt technologies. To do this, we confirm the null hypothesis and reject the affirmative hypothesis.

THEME 6: Reason for the lack of employment after a technical training course in a given establishment.

Table 7 below shows the results relating to the different reasons for the lack of employment on the part of the young adult technician.

Null hypothesis: the lack of employment is due to the unavailability of vacant positions and insufficient professional experience.

Alternative hypothesis: the lack of employment after a training course is due to the lack of opportunity.

Table 7: Presentation and analysis of data relating to the lack of employment

Response (k)	f_0	f_t	$f_0 - f_t$	$(f_0 - f_t)^2$	$(f_0 - f_t)^2 / f_t$
Lack of employment relative to the technical sector followed	12	10	2	4	0.4
Lack of opportunity	8	10	-2	4	0.4
Lack of availability of vacant positions	9	10	-1	1	0.1
Insufficient professional experience.	11	10	1	1	0.1
Total	40			10	1

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 11, Issue 6, pp: (59-68), Month: November - December 2024, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

The theoretical frequency f_t being respectively 12, 8, 9 and 11 for the observed frequencies

f_0 of 10; the degree of freedom is then: $DI=k-1=4-1=3$ From where: the calculated value is: 1; the tabulated value at the threshold of 0.05 (5%) being 7.82

The data in Table 8 above show that out of 40 participants, 12 give as a reason: the lack of employment is due to the technical training sector followed; 8 say that it is a problem of lack of opportunity; 9 think that this is due to the lack of availability of vacant positions in in the field of training; and 11 say that it is a problem of insufficient professional experience. The degree of freedom being equal to 3, gives at the threshold of 0.05 a tabulated Chi-square value of 7.82 higher than the calculated Chi-square of 1.

Conclusion: In view of the results obtained by calculation through the data in Table 8; the reason for the lack of employment after a technical training course followed in an educational structure would be to decide between the lack of vacant positions in the field of training and the insufficient professional experience. To do this, we affirm the null hypothesis.

THEME 7: Duration of the school post training or academic position and nature of the training.

Table 8 below summarizes the results relating to the deadline of the training.

Null hypothesis: this training must be provided during short practical sessions.

Alternative hypothesis: the training given must be done for a short period of time following the real need of employers.

Table 8: Presentation and analysis of data relating to the duration of post-school or academic training

Response (k)	f_0	f_t	f_0-f_t	$(f_0-f_t)^2$	$(f_0-f_t)^2/f_t$
Very long practical sessions	10	10	0	0	0
Fairly long practical sessions	4	10	-6	36	3.6
Short practical sessions as needed	24	10	14	196	19.6
Very short practical sessions	2	10	-8	64	6.4
Total	40			10	29.6

The theoretical frequency f_t being respectively 10, 4, 24 and 2 for the observed frequencies

f_0 of 10; the degree of freedom is then: $DI=k-1=4-1=3$; From which: the calculated value is: 29.6; the tabulated value at the threshold of 0.05 (5%) being 7.82

The data in Table 9 above show that out of 40 participants, 10 are of the opinion that this training should be done in very long practical sessions; 4 say that fairly long sessions are preferable against 24 who say that this training should be organized in short practical sessions according to the needs of the young adult; while 2 participants advocate for very short practical sessions. The degree of freedom being equal to 3, gives at the threshold of 0.05 a tabulated Chi-square value of 7.82 lower than the calculated Chi-square of 29.6.

Conclusion: In view of the results obtained by calculation through the data in Table III.6; the duration of post-school or academic training should be organized in short practical sessions according to the need to facilitate the easy integration of the young adult after this training. To do this, we reject the null hypothesis.

THEME 8: Most sought-after technical training sector

Table 9 below shows the results relating to the most employable sector in some technical fields in our environment.

Null hypothesis: all technical sectors are employable because they offer the possibility of moving from one field to another

Alternative hypothesis: not all technical sectors offer the possibility of being employable, but only some.

Table 9: Presentation and analysis of data relating to the most popular sector

Response (k)	f_0	f_t	$f_0 - f_t$	$(f_0 - f_t)^2$	$(f_0 - f_t)^2 / f_t$
Electricity	3	4	-1	1	0.25
Electronics	3	4	-1	1	0.25
Computer science	4	4	0	0	0
Construction	4	4	0	0	0
Mechanics	3	4	-1	1	0.25
Automotive mechanics	3	4	-1	1	0.25
Metallurgy	4	4	0	0	0
Heavy goods vehicle driving	6	4	2	4	1
Mining	3	4	-1	1	0.25
All sectors	7	4	-3	9	2.25
Total	40			18	4.5

The theoretical frequency f_t being respectively 3, 3, 4, 4, 3, 3, 4, 6, 3, and 7 for the observed frequencies f_0 of 4; the degree of freedom is then: $DI = k - 1 = 10 - 1 = 9$; From where: the calculated value is: 4.5; the tabulated value at the threshold of 0.05 (5%) being 16.92.

The data in table 10 above show that out of 40 participants, 3 are for electricity; 3 for electronics; 4 for IT; 4 for construction; 3 for mechanics; 3 for automobile mechanics, 4 for metallurgy, 6 for heavy goods vehicle driving, 3 for mining, and 7 affirm that all technical sectors are in demand in our environment. The degree of freedom being equal to 9, gives at the threshold of 0.05 a tabulated Chi-square value of 16.92 higher than the calculated Chi-square of 4.5.

Conclusion: In view of the results obtained by calculation through the data in Table 10; we affirm that all sectors are in demand in our environment. To do this, we confirm the null hypothesis.

Interpretation of the results

In view of the results obtained by calculation through the data in Table 2 relating to access to basic training and access to employment by young adult technicians; after analysis, we affirm that access to employment is difficult in our environment after an apprenticeship course in an educational establishment.

On the one hand, this is based on the fact that several establishments organizing technical training do not have workshops and laboratories that meet the technological standards in force which require that the young adult trained have the skills to meet the requirements of the job market in general through purely practical teaching, and not theoretical in the case of our environment.

It is said that: it is from practice that theory emerges and not the other way around.

On the other hand, the inexperience of the young adult technician prevents him from being hired directly after his course; because they say: "a picture is worth a thousand words".

As for the second theme relating to the reasons for going through basic training before professional integration; in view of the results obtained by calculation through the data in Table 3; the reason that would push young adults to request specific training before applying for a job would be the incompatibility between the training received at school and the technological realities of the position applied for.

The young adult after technical training in an establishment, most often realizes a mismatch between the training received during his course and the realities of the position he is applying for.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and LearningVol. 11, Issue 6, pp: (59-68), Month: November - December 2024, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

In most cases, the positions require know-how while the young adult does not have any because he receives in most cases theoretical technical training without suitable equipment on the one hand and on the other with obsolete equipment that does not correspond to technological realities.

The young person trained sometimes finds himself without the technical basis necessary for his integration, hence the saying: "why train?" As for the third theme relating to the importance of post-school/academic training; the data in Table 6 show that the need for extracurricular training is a real need in our environment in certain subjects relating to the practice not learned by the young adult during his course, with a particular emphasis on felt technologies.

Faced with this reality, the young adult trained is obliged to perfect his training through other specific training courses because he does not have know-how on recent technologies not available in the national programs of our country in general but also during his course, the young person is sometimes not aware of the realities of the professional environment because several companies full of redescent technologies set a tailor-made criterion to prevent the latter from making visits or internships with a view to professional experience adapted to the requirements of the employing companies. Benoit Brassier and José Rose (March 2018) emphasize that experience in a profession among the learner can only be acquired through the following means: Professional internships; Academic internships; Summer / vacation internships; Volunteering / volunteering opportunities; Research projects within companies; International programs; Occasional / part-time work and Freelance work. These different means are not always possible in view of the realities of our environment. The fourth theme deals with access to employment for young adults in Likasi.

Through the data in Table 3; access to employment after an apprenticeship course is difficult in our environment. This is proven by the fact that the inexperience of the young person and the lack of preparation for professional integration characterize the young adult trained in the Democratic Republic of Congo in general but particularly in urban areas such as the city of Likasi.

According to Colley (2002), "management has a role to play in building a school culture that is favorable to the integration of beginners." Indeed, management must ensure that professional integration is considered a collective responsibility, shared by all members of the staff of the educational institution.

As for the number of trainees, it should be noted that our environment has several young adults who have followed a normal course in a technical establishment but in view of the growing number of technicians disbursed each year on the job market both in technical humanities and at the higher and university levels; access to a position becomes complex because the available positions remain lower than those trained.

The fifth theme deals with the reasons why, despite technical training followed in a technical education structure, the young adult remains unemployed. In view of the results obtained by calculation through the data in Table 5; The reasons for the lack of employment after a technical training course followed in an educational structure would be to divide between the lack of vacancies in the training field and the lack of professional experience.

Addressing the first aspect relating to the lack of vacancies in several technical fields, this is verified by the fact that educational planning at both the national and local levels is not effective. According to MASHIKA Michel (2021) in his in-depth study thesis from the University of California shows that the Democratic Republic of Congo has only around 14,000 companies for an active population of around 920,000,000.

This situation proves that the available companies are not able to cover the various job demands of young candidates. As for the second aspect of this theme relating to the lack of professional experience, the young adult trained in the conditions of almost finishing his apprenticeship course without the required professional experience that could allow him to meet the requirements of job offers from employing companies, imposing conditions beyond his skills can only find himself unemployed despite the technical training done.

The sixth theme deals with the duration of post-school or academic training. In view of the results obtained by calculation through the data in Table 8; the duration of post-school or academic training must be organized in short practical sessions as needed to facilitate the easy integration of the young adult after this training.

The young adult who has completed a technical training course in an establishment needs to understand the reason for another training; hence the concept of interest must be taken into consideration as John DEWEY said quoted by KALENGA

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 11, Issue 6, pp: (59-68), Month: November - December 2024, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

MWENZEMI (2017): "interest is the driving force behind actions". Without interest, the latter will immediately tire of the training.

The seventh theme is about the most sought-after technical field in our environment. In view of the results obtained by calculation through the data in Table 9 stating that all fields are sought-after in our environment, it is important for the young adult to understand this in order not to fall into negligence and underestimation of their capacities.

As Mohamed Jihad pointed out in his article entitled: Mother Science; no science can claim to be above the others because they all form a whole for complementarity.

Thus, all technical training fields in our environment are employable.

In the last theme relating to entrepreneurship following the training sector. In view of the results obtained by calculation through the data in Table 4, we affirm that the possibility of undertaking in several areas of technical training is there; and this implies confidence on the part of consumers of the services offered. The young adult trained in a given technical field has the possibility of embarking on certain activities without waiting for a salaried job from any company.

For KAWASAKI Guy (2019); "the best reason to start a business is to create meaning, to create a product or service that contributes to improving the world".

A study by the Observatory of Economic Francophonie (OFE) created in June 2017 by the University of Montreal, in partnership with the Government of Quebec, the International Organization of La Francophonie (OIF) and the University Agency of La Francophonie (AUF) shows an analysis of the recent evolution of youth employment in the DRC that entrepreneurship should be considered as a way out of the proliferation of unemployment.

5. SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Through this study focused on access to training and employability of young adults in the city of Likasi; we formulate some suggestions and proposals in order to make access to employment effective.

- For young adults: young adults must in a particular way appropriate the technical training received in a technical education structure by seeking a center of interest in new technologies in the field followed in order to respond to the agreements of employing companies while seeking certain means of acquiring professional skills, such as: Professional internships; Academic internships; Holiday internships; Volunteering opportunities; Research projects within companies; International programs; Casual/part-time work; Freelance work

For technical education institutions: that the educational structures work in collaboration with the various surrounding societies with a view to developing a good policy of good impression. The latter will allow each establishment to put young learners in contact with the technological realities used in modern societies. That each structure organizes it self to facilitate and multiply practical sessions in order to provide them with adequate professional experience. Each technical establishment organizes itself to have a laboratory and a workshop for each organized sector.

- For the government organizing education: the government must, through its missions, ensure the effectiveness of technical education with a view to putting in place binding measures for the opening of a technical education structure. That the recommendations aimed at valuing young people trained be made available to employing companies with a view to facilitating their task of carrying out professional internships; academic internships; vacation internships; volunteering opportunities; research projects within companies; casual / part-time work, freelance work. That entrepreneurship be popularized in the national education program.

That the state puts projects to support young people in the realization and concretization of the results and solutions developed by young people through their end-of-cycle work but also their end-of-study work.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on access to technical training and the employability of young adults in the City of Likasi, the content of this article shows the difficulty that Likasian youth have in particular in accessing quality training to find a way in the search for employment.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 11, Issue 6, pp: (59-68), Month: November - December 2024, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

The results of our research constitute a prototype for the development of a technical training plan for a school or academic position for sustainable and assured employability in our country in general and in our environment in particular. For future researchers who are interested in this theme, we suggest completing the model by drawing up a teaching program for each technical field.

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